

E-Commerce in Education Programmes a Way to Solve Unemployment Amongst Education Graduates

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ABSTRACT

This paper argues the need to include e-commerce as a subject in Education programs to enhance our students' employment chances of education graduates in Nigeria. The study was conducted using the survey research method. The population of the study comprises 330 Business Education students in two universities in Anambra state. The research was carried out in Nnamdi Azikiwe University and students of Abia State University. A questionnaire was used for data collection and a sample of 130 Business Education students was collected for the study, out of which 90 were dully filled and completed. The findings revealed that the knowledge of e-commerce skills has great usefulness and importance on companies and enterprises giving the graduates of Business education an employment advantage. E-commerce education has a positive impact on the Business Education program. The study recommended that the program should be given their rightful place in the Business Education program and they should also be accorded equal recognition as other programs in the Business Education Department.

INTRODUCTION

In simple terms, commerce means the exchange of goods and services in any society. In a broader sense, commerce is that part of Business that is concerned with the exchange of goods and services and includes all those activities that directly or indirectly facilitate that exchange. It can further be said to mean taking trade to another level the exchange of goods and services between members of a society which is also known as commerce has been done traditionally through the different ages, but due to advancements in technology, different kinds of business could also be carried out through the electronic system. Now, this is commonly known as e-commerce, which consists of the buying and selling of products or services over electronic systems through the use of the Internet and other computer networks. The World Trade Organization defines e-commerce as the production, distribution, marketing, sales, or delivery of goods and services by electronic means. E-commerce draws on technologies such as mobile commerce, electronic funds transfer, supply chain management, internet Marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems, and automated data collection systems.

Technology has come to stay and so has e-commerce which has a lot to offer to our changing world today. In Nigeria, the advent of e-commerce brought about positive changes among the people and the society at large. Through the use of e-commerce in different forms, most Nigerians now live comfortably with the services rendered to satisfy their human needs, both companies and the educational sector should understand how important it is to move along with the changing world. E-commerce as some scholars would call it has been tremendously used by most developing countries in the world whereby Nigeria is part of them. It has lots of benefits, some of which are: economic benefits, social benefits, educational benefits, and global benefits, etc. Among these, we shall concentrate on the educational aspects of e-commerce, and how e-commerce education can be infused, combined, or integrated into our educational system through business education programs in higher institutions. But with this, one would want to understand what Business Education is and how the need for e-commerce in Business Education arose.

The challenge of Unemployment is a national challenge in Nigeria that can account for the establishment of Business education. Business Education was formed to prepare beneficiaries for gainful employment and sustainable livelihood. It is generally seen as an education concerned about business activities. Business Education for business is that aspect of vocational education that gives learning and preparation for office work egg clerks, secretaries, shorthand-typist or stenographers, bookkeepers, data processors, word processors, computer analysts, and ICT experts. Our world is fast changing and becoming more advanced with the advent of technology. Due to the presence of this technology, occupations like shorthand and stenography which is one of the important skills obtained in Business education have gradually been shoved away. Where secretaries and personal assistants could easily record and video meetings with different kinds of computer gadgets, therefore, there is little or

no need for shorthand writing or stenography which in turn keeps graduates of Business Education out of work. But when e-commerce is infused into Business Education, it would stand as a replacement for shorthand and stenography thereby, producing competent and skills-full individuals to suit the demands of employers.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of infusion and availability of e-commerce in Business Education programs by tertiary institutions in Nigeria?
2. How useful and important would the skill be in our business world today?
3. What is the impact of e-commerce and its institutional placement?
4. Does e-commerce improve students' performance in studying Business education?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Business teaching involves exposing students to the essential rudiments, assumptions, and methods of business, teaching in this discipline takes place at various stages starting from secondary education and institution of higher education or university education. Roughly 38% of students register for one or more courses in Business education while at the secondary school level. So many students at the university level take business courses as a major, this interconnected field, or a career in teaching academics. In university, students have the chance to enroll in general business courses or to enroll for a particular degree in business studies. The courses accessible differ by school but mainly include essential and fundamental selections like accounting, marketing, finance, and business management. Definite curricular and degree-granting happenings vary to some extent by course and by state or school. The curriculum of Business Education is decision-making capability. A bachelor's degree offered in Business education includes:

1. Bachelor of Science in Business Education (BSCE).An Undergraduate Degree in the Teaching of Business.
2. Bachelor of Accountancy, specialized Accountancy Degree
3. Bachelor in Business
4. Bachelor in Business Administration (BBA). A Bachelor's Degree in Business Administration
5. Bachelor of Business Science (BBUSSC).A Business Degree with a focus on Management Theory and Quantitative Underpin Education
6. Bachelor of Commerce. A Bachelor in Business Teacher Education (BBTE). A Variant on the BSBE.
7. Undergraduate degree in Commerce, etc

The Business Education program is designed in such a way that a student can concentrate in four noted areas that make up Business Education such as:

- a. Secretarial Education
- b. Accounting Education

- c. Distributive or Marketing Education
- d. Office Occupations Education

The problems confronting achieving integration of e-commerce in Business Education mostly have to do with the question of what is the appropriate organizational placement for e-commerce. The literature reflects three primary views on the issue:

1. It should be treated as a distinct discipline
2. It should be fully integrated into the functional business education curriculum
3. It may be treated as a separate discipline initially, but should ultimately (or inevitably) be integrated into the general business school curriculum.

Most articles present a balance of opinions on the various dimensions of institutional placement, especially popular media articles. Nevertheless, the opinions articulated by the proponents of one position or the other are clearly and often bluntly expressed. Apart from these major challenges, there are other challenges towards the integration of practical e-commerce programs some of which are firstly enlisting the support of all faculty and administration because this type of program requires high levels of effort and commitment. This includes a commitment by faculty to keep up-to-date. Besides reading the literature, faculty must attend workshops and work closely with businesses. Another challenge concerns acquiring hardware and software. The institution should try to assist faculty by providing the appropriate hardware and software, which is no small task considering the rate of change in the e-commerce area. What then is the origin of all today's e-commerce? Here lies an age-old question what came first, the egg or the chicken, or in our case-commerce or civilization? Since science and already solved the mystery of the first hatched chicken (spoilers: the egg came first), we shall move toward our part of the equation. Arguably, we could say that the history of commerce is also the history of civilization. It does not exactly answer, but it does shed some light on chronologically the darkest part of our kind. There wasn't a single society capable of producing every single thing it desired. As we have met some needs, others arose with time. This fundamental principle is precisely with necessitated the trade among each other.

E-commerce Website

1. E-commerce and websites mean your understanding of what an e-commerce site is.
2. What truly separates it from the rest is its internal division based upon the types of business with which it deals.
3. Traditional Retail; inch by long inch, we are getting closer to a complete transformation of traditional retail. We are eliminating the need to carry any cash at any given moment or even to pick up our groceries. In turn, we get more leisure time to spend with our loved ones, good books, or even a walk in a park instead of the usual walk in a parking lot.

Jobs

The 20th century was mainly an era of high growth of factory workers, and now unfortunately the present era is making those same workers redundant. It is a hard truth to accept, we know, but there is light at the end of that rabbit hole. E-commerce is a job provider, period. Amazon is employing over 300,000 staff working for its organization. Not only that. Digital companies are expanding all over the world. It's not just in America only, but all over the world. China's growth in 2016 was even more impressive, surpassing the retail growth by twice as much.

Prompt Information Response

Having information at easy reach is a great instance of the numerous benefits of e-commerce to every society.

Entertainment

The influence of e-commerce has also influenced the entertainment industry music and movies are easily downloaded and played seemingly without stress.

Online learning

In recent times people attend classes and conduct all manner of educational activities through online learning making education easy and accessible.

E-commerce and Trade

Online interactions have boosted commerce and trade globally.

Finally, in the context of relationship development, e-commerce initiatives in internal administration can help a business build stronger relationships with its partners and suppliers by sharing information continuously and by implementing accounting/financial management practices that enable quicker, more transparent transactions.

Business Teaching

The need for the study of business education in Nigeria was triggered by the report of the Commission on post-school certificates and higher education in Nigeria popularly known as. The Ashby report emphasized the need for business education in Nigeria, the report noted that there was a dearth of trained secretaries, bookkeepers, and accountants to fill clerical and junior administrative posts both in the civil services and in the business community. So there was a growing need for business knowledge in Nigeria as a result of the quest for fast development efforts in the country. As consumers, people need to increase their business knowledge so that they may select from among the vast quantities of goods and services. It was apparent that many Nigerians have come to realize that they need training and skills that could make them

employable. So you can see that people in all works of life tend to attach much importance to business education.

People need the knowledge acquired in business education since employment requirements are changing. Therefore employers require people with business education skills and competencies as the prerequisite for entry into and advancement in the world of work. So secondary and post-secondary institutions must have a strong, comprehensive, well-articulated business education program that is characterized by a flexible delivery system. The dual mission of Business Education which is to provide education FOR AND ABOUT Business must be promoted in every secondary and post-secondary Business Education program.

When this is done:

1. The vocational objective of Business Education could be accomplished by providing programmers who will prepare people for employment in Business or as owner's managers of business enterprises.
2. Basic business and economic education objectives could be accomplished by providing courses and experiences about business and the like which at the same time strengthens their basic reading, writing, mathematical, and interpersonal skills.

E-Commerce Teaching

The need for the study of e-commerce education started as a result of authors on post-school certificates and higher education in Nigeria. Their report emphasized the need for e-commerce education in Nigeria. The report noted that there was a dearth of trained individuals who were good with information technology and internet trade to fill up positions in the management of a company that has decided to go global in the business community. So there is a growing need for knowledge in information technology, as a result of the quest for fast development efforts in the country. The internet and technology have come to stay therefore the sooner we get acquainted with the technological system the better it shall become for the nation. It is important to note that we have come to realize that we need training and skills that could make us employable. So you can see that people from all walks of life tend to attach much importance to e-commerce teaching.

We need the knowledge and information we acquired from ICT considering our constantly changing World as such employers are asking for people with skills and competencies as the prerequisite for entry into and advancement in the world of work and occupation. Note that the need for Business Education has been to eradicate the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria and it has been very effective until recently due to the advent of technology, which has made life much easier and faster. This is the 21st century where technology is taking charge of every aspect of our lives. Commerce is no longer done only through the brick-and-mortar form but also digitally through the use of internet services which is called e-commerce. Due to the fast and growing nature of e-commerce and its benefits which would help in employment issues in Nigeria, it is too welcomed into Business Education. E-

commerce programs are the educational juncture at which business and technology intersect. Most articles note that some mix of these two keystones of e-commerce is appropriate and inevitable.

METHODOLOGY

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire on strategies for examining the need for e-commerce integration in Business Education programs for employability, section A deals with the personal data of the respondents while section B concentrated on the questionnaire item. Four Likert types of response were adopted as shown below:

SD = Strongly Disagree	=4	(VHE) Very High extent	= 4
D= Disagree	=3	(HE) High Extent	= 3
A = Agree		(VLE) Low Extent	= 2
SA = Strongly Agree	= 1	LE) Very Low Extent	= 1

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using mean and presented in the tables according to the research questions. The mean (X) response of the respondent was calculated using the formula:

$$= \frac{\sum FX}{N}$$

Where

E = summation

F= frequency of even score

X = any score in the distribution

N = total number of scores in the distribution

$$\text{Thus } X = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

Decision role: any response receiving a mean (X) score of 3.0 and above was a high extent and a mean (X) score rating less than 3.0 was a low extent.

That is $X > 3.0$ = High Extent

$X < 3.0$ = Low Extent

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained from the study was analyzed here with the presentation of the result as follows:

Research Question 1

To what extent is the infusion and availability of e-commerce in Business Education programs by tertiary institutions in Nigeria?

Table 1. Respondents Rating on the Aims and Objectives of Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme?

N = 90	
S/N	Items on the Extent of Integration and Availability
X	Remarks
of E-commerce in Business Education	
1.	To what extent is the availability of e-commerce 2.10 low extent in the Business Education program in your school?
2.	To what extent are you aware of the availability of a 2.56 high-extent e-commerce course in your program as a Business Education student?
3.	To what extent do students of Business Education 2.31 low extent Study e-commerce as part of their program?
4.	What is the extent of availability of lecturers for 2.02 low extent the course e-commerce in your school?
GRAND MEAN	2.25 low exte

The data in Table 1 shows the mean rating of the extent of integration and availability of e-commerce in Business Education programs. The respondents were provided with four questions on the integration and availability of e-commerce in the Business Education program. In the table, it was indicated that item (2) had a greater mean of 2.5 which is regarded as a high extent. The grand mean of this category is 2.25 which shows that the research question was answered to be on the low extent.

Research Question 2

How useful and important would e-commerce skills be in our business world today?

Table 2. Respondent Rating on the Usefulness and Importance of E-commerce Skills in Business Today.

S/N	Items on the usefulness and importance of e-commerce remark skills on companies and enterprises	X
1.	Managers and employers are in search of individuals e-commerce skills	3.40 agree with
2.	E-commerce prepares Business Education students employment in industries and companies	2.81 agree To fit in
3.	Managers and employers like graduates of Business Education with e-commerce skills	2.92 agree on
4.	Employers would rather pick Business Education 2.40 disagree graduates with e-commerce skills than other graduates who study technological courses?	
5.	Graduates of Business Education with e-commerce skill 3.12 agree would be of great use to industries and companies who want to go global	
GRAND MEAN		2.93 Agree

The data in Table 2 indicates that there is a lot of importance and usefulness of e-commerce skills in businesses today. The respondents were provided with items regarding the question and item (8) had a mean of 2.4 which was regarded as disagree. The other four items had a mean of 2.5 above which was regarded as agree. The grand mean of this category is 2.93 showing that the research questions were agreed upon. The entire items agreed on the usefulness of e-commerce skills in the business world today.

Research question 3

What is the impact of e-commerce on the Business education curriculum?

Table 3. Respondent Rating on the Impact of E-commerce in Business Education Curriculum.

1.	The presence of e-commerce helps in fulfilling goal 3.76 and the objectives of Business Education		
2.	E-commerce adds to the skills and knowledge obtained by students in Business Education	3.25	agree
3.	Infusion of e-commerce in Business Education helps to improve the standards of Business Education	3.29	agree
4.	The interdisciplinary nature of e-commerce corresponds with some courses offered in business Education which makes it so efficient for the program	2.64	
GRAND MEAN		2.97	agree

Table 3 above shows the impact of e-commerce in Business Education programs. The respondent was provided with an item regarding the question and all items had a mean above 2.5 which was regarded as agreed. The grand mean of the category is 2.97 which shows that the research question was answered to agreed.

Research Question 4

To what extent does e-commerce improve students' performance in studying Business Education?

Table 4. Respondent rating on the improvement of students' performance in Business Education through the study of e-commerce.

S/N	Items on the extent to which e-commerce course Remark	X
	Improves students' performance in studying Business Education	
1.	To what extent will students be able to do a good job through the combination of business Education with the learning of e-commerce?	3.18 high-extent
2.	To what extent will students be conversant with technologies like computers, projectors internet, etc. through the study of e-commerce	2.77 high-extent

3. E-commerce helps students to acquire skills and Knowledge necessary for office work	3.01 high extent
4. Students perform well in Business Education through the interdisciplinary nature of e-commerce	2.60 high extents of
GRAND MEAN	2.89 high extent

The data in Table 4 shows the mean rating of the extent to which e-commerce courses improve students' performance in studying Business Education. The respondents were provided with four questions on the improvement of students' performance in studying Business Education. In the table, it was indicated that all items were more than 2.5 which is regarded as high extent. The grand mean of this category is 2.89 which shows that the research question was answered to be on a high extent.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The problems militating against the integration of e-commerce into Business Education programs include lack of equipment or insufficient equipment, insufficient number of qualified teachers, and prejudicial attitude of society toward Business Education. It is therefore wise on the part of the government to provide for and solve these problems since Business Education programs are relevant to the operations of the organization.

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. The introduction of e-commerce education programs is relevant and useful in the Department of Business Education, and the program should be given its rightful place in our school curriculum.
2. There is a need to train more Business Education teachers on e-commerce education in Colleges of Education and departments of Business Education and Vocational Education in universities.
3. There is the need to encourage teachers of Business Education programs should be encouraged. They should be paid an allowance like their science counterparts.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic is still needed "E-Commerce in Education Programmes a Way to Solve Unemployment Amongst Education Graduates."

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